

Article Title: Security and privacy in physical activity chatbots on social media:
A scoping review

Search Strategy – 12th February 2024

Database	Query	Results
PubMed	((conversational agent[Title/Abstract]) OR (virtual agent[Title/Abstract])) OR (chatbot[Title/Abstract]) AND (((physical activity[Title/Abstract]) OR (exercise[Title/Abstract])) OR (fitness[Title/Abstract])) OR (physical fitness[Title/Abstract]))	8
IEEE Xplore	((Abstract:conversational agent) OR (Abstract:virtual agent) OR (Abstract:chatbot)) AND ((Abstract:physical activity) OR (Abstract:exercise) OR (Abstract:fitness) OR (Abstract:physical fitness))	109
ACM	[[Abstract: "physical activity"] OR [Abstract: exercise] OR [Abstract: fitness] OR [Abstract: "physical fitness"]] AND [[Abstract: "conversational agent"] OR [Abstract: "virtual agent"] OR [Abstract: chatbot]]	1096
PyscINFO	1 (conversational agent or virtual agent or chatbot).ab. 2 (physical activity or exercise or fitness or physical fitness).ab. 3 1 and 2	10
Total		1299